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Context Aware Sliding Work Sharing for Human-AI Collaboration in Logistics Domain

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Abstract. This paper introduces a novel framework for context-aware sliding work sharing (SWS) to enhance human-AI collaboration. It addresses the challenge of dynamically balancing human and machine contributions by leveraging real-time contextual information and machine confidence levels. The proposed system integrates advanced context awareness mechanisms — comprising context modelling, monitoring, and extraction — with adaptive SWS management to facilitate informed task delegation between humans and AI/robots. By adjusting autonomy levels based on situational complexity and user expertise, the approach aims to improve decision-making, efficiency, and trust in AI-supported environments. A logistics-based use case demonstrates the practical applicability and potential benefits of the system.

Keywords: Context awareness · Sliding work sharing · Human-AI collaboration · Logistics · Adaptive autonomy · Decision support

1 Introduction

AI and robotics are likely to be the most powerful means for radical improvement of working conditions in diverse domains such as industry, logistics, healthcare, construction, agriculture, education etc. AI and robots can support human operators in diverse tasks starting from difficult and tedious manual labour tasks up to complex decision-making tasks. This paper addresses the approach of the AI4Work project [1] to support the operation of complex systems with general questions such as how to increase efficiency of work, reduce the stress upon employees or increase confidence in decision-making tasks. In particular, the main question that we aim to answer is how to optimally share the work between humans and AI/robots. We provide an overview of the topics relevant for this work, namely on context awareness and sliding work sharing (section 2), follow with the vision for the proposed Context Aware Sliding Work Sharing (section 3) and support this with the Context Awareness and Sliding Work Sharing tools (section 4). Finally, we describe a potential application in the logistic sector and some conclusions.

2 Overview of State of the Art

2.1 Context Awareness

The context under which work activities are carried out is of a high relevance for both (a) accuracy/reliability of AI recommendations/activities and (b) acceptance of these actions by the users. (a) The context under which data are acquired and processed may have a high influence upon collaborative decision making. As indicated in [2], the meaning of many concepts heavily depends on some implicit context, and changes in that context can cause radical changes in concepts. Incremental concept learning in such domains requires the ability to recognize and adapt to such changes. This is particularly the case in modern organisations, where the context under which the work processes are carried out changes very often. For example, faults in manufacturing and logistics processes have different meaning and weight if the equipment is in installation and ramp-up, or in normal (stationary) production phase, or if there is a change in a configuration of a production line due to changes in demands, etc. (b) The interpretation of the context under which a recommendation by AI is proposed or actions by AI/robots are performed is important to better understand why a specific recommendation/actions is made by the AI/robot module, i.e. to allow for an improved traceability of the AI recommendations. It is expected that this would lead to better acceptance of AI-supported decision making and activities in organisations.

Context Awareness is a concept propagated in various domains, such as ubiquitous computing and AI. It is the idea that computers can be both sensitive and reactive, based on their environment [3].

It is difficult to find a single definition for the notion of context, but its importance in communication, categorization, intelligent information retrieval and knowledge representation has been recognized for many years. In the AI domain, the concept of context is usually defined as the generalization of a collection of assumptions [4], [5]. A common, pragmatic definition for context-aware applications, defines context as “any information that can be used to characterize the situation of an entity. An entity is a person, place, or object that is considered relevant to the interaction between a user and an application, including the user and application themselves” [6], [7]. The current research on knowledge context is primarily oriented towards capturing and utilization of contextual data for actionable knowledge [2], [8]. A number of systems to handle context awareness were proposed by the research community [9], [10], [11]. Thereby an important aspect is to make the data available for contextual analysis and processing. Various solutions for monitoring and ingesting data into contextual analytics services are available, e.g. U-QASAR [12], SAFIRE Context Monitoring Framework [13] or FIware Context Broker [14].

The key elements of context awareness solutions are context models (that describe the situation) and context extractors which identify often in real time the current context to which the ICT environment has to adapt. The basis for context-aware applications is a well-designed Context Model. As context integrates different knowledge sources and binds knowledge to the user to guarantee that the understanding is consistent, context modelling is extensively investigated within knowledge management research [3].

Different kinds of contexts should be represented in a common “language” when possible, but the representation must be extensible enough to support domain and application specific concepts. Typical context modelling techniques include key-value models, object-oriented models, and ontological methods [15]. A semantic model (or ontology) provides a representation flexible enough to support common modelling of context in a structured way, as well as domain specific extension to the model, thus it is chosen for representation purposes. Ontology based modelling is considered the most promising approach, as it enables a formal analysis of the domain knowledge, promoting contextual knowledge sharing and reuse in a ubiquitous computing system, and context reasoning based on semantic web technologies [16] [17]. Up to now there were only limited “industrial driven” attempts to provide harmonised modelling of context under which data from human-AI/robot collaboration are generated. The problem to be solved is how to extract context from human-AI/robot collaboration. Since it is planned to model the context with ontologies, the context extraction is mainly an issue of context reasoning and context provisioning: how to inference high level context information from low level raw context data [18] and [19]. Based on the formal description of context information, context can be processed with contextual reasoning mechanisms [20] [21]. There are three main categories of reasoning, deductive reasoning, event-condition-action reasoning and statistical reasoning which can be distinguished.

Context awareness is of special importance in the human-AI/robot collaboration in various domains and used under dynamically changing conditions and by various users [22]. The most challenging aspect of the application of the context awareness for human-AI/robot collaboration is an effective acquisition/collection of data needed to extract the current context. Therefore, the advanced collection of data, is a basic prerequisite for an effective application of this approach in different sectors. The key challenge is to identify cost-effective ways to obtain data needed for context extraction. The context awareness features of the AI4Work services consider as basis important outcomes of solutions developed in the projects SelfLearning [19, 22], K-NET, SAFIRE [23], DIVERSITY [24], and in SmartCLIDE [25]. The context extractor will be re-used, but the context models will have to be adapted and extended to meet process requirements (e.g., to extend the model, in addition to concepts such as location, time, activity, with concepts relevant for processes, all other concepts that can be relevant for a human operator, etc.).

2.2 Sliding Work Sharing (SWS)

The AI4Work project investigates practical methods and tools for optimal sharing of work between humans and AI/robots. In this context, "sliding work sharing" is defined as an approach where the balance between human and machine activities varies during the operation, depending on the situational context, machine-based confidence levels and human interactions [1]. This term and definition were inspired by the similar definition of "sliding decision making", as presented in [27].

The term "sliding work sharing" (SWS) was introduced by the AI4Work project proposal [1], therefore no prior scientific literature can be found about SWS. However, the related concept of "sliding autonomy" could be identified, which is considered

highly relevant as basis for AI4Work's research on SWS. Sliding autonomy, also called "adjustable autonomy", was researched extensively in the domains of robotics and (multi-)agent systems [27]. Instead of having fixed modes like "robot working autonomously" or "human teleoperating the robot", the aim is to vary the level of autonomy during operation, depending on the respective situation. The motivation for this approach is that, on the one hand, highly autonomous robots can help reducing the mental load of human operators [28] and they can also be used in hostile environments, where humans may not be able to work [29] [30], but on the other hand, it is hardly possible (or very time-consuming) to program robots in a way that they can react to all potential challenges that may happen in dynamic real-world environments [29], [28], [31]. Therefore, humans should at least monitor the robots' work and should be able to intervene in case of robots "being stuck" or in case of potential safety hazards. Another motivation for sliding autonomy may be to dynamically adjust the robots' autonomy level depending on the skill level of the human who is controlling the robot [32].

Different scenarios regarding sliding autonomy are discussed in the existing literature, involving either single robots (e.g. [32]) or teams of robots, either being supervised by humans (e.g. [29] [28]) or working with humans in peer-to-peer mode (i.e. humans are working together with robots on the same task or can even get tasks assigned by robots, e.g. [27] [31]), solving different experimental tasks. Aiming to simplify the description, the example of "one human and one robot working together" is used in the following, however the general principles apply also to multi-robot/multi-human teams.

A variety of potential levels of autonomy may be differentiated, e.g. considering the ten levels of automation suggested in [33]. However, when considering sliding autonomy of robots, the three main levels that are most relevant can be summarized as follows:

- Fully autonomous: the robot is working autonomously, without any human involvement.
- Intermediate: the robot is in general working autonomously, but a human can temporarily provide support or take over control.
- Manual operation: the human operates the robot, having full control over it.

A temporal human involvement, as indicated in the intermediate autonomy level above, is typically caused by an unexpected issue that either prevents the robot from continuing its work or that decreases the performance of its work. Such unplanned human involvements may be "triggered" by either human or robot, so two basic scenarios can be differentiated:

- The robot itself detects an issue and informs the human that it requires support. This may happen for different reasons, e.g.
 - the robot is blocked/trapped or is lost in the environment [27],
 - considering a given task, the robot has a low level of "self-confidence" regarding its ability to succeed [30],
 - a timeout occurred, i.e. the robot did not succeed after a specific time or number of tries [29], [31],
 - the robot actively assigns a task to a human, which is relevant in peer-to-peer human-robot teams [27].
- The human pro-actively intervenes because they observe one of the following:

- the robot's work seems inefficient and thus efficiency improvements are possible through human intervention [29],
- the robot is behaving incorrectly [31],
- the robot may become a safety hazard (e.g. due to potential collisions with surrounding objects, other robots, or even humans) [29], [30], [32],
- there may be a risk of losing the robot, which is especially relevant when working in hostile environments where humans can only teleoperate the robot [30].

Different studies about sliding autonomy did experiments (either physical or simulated) to compare the performance (including required time, error rate, workload for human operator) of sliding autonomy compared to robots being either fully autonomous or under full control of humans, e.g. [27-29, 31, 32]. Although these experiments usually comprise only a limited number of repetitions of a very specific task, some general patterns can be observed. Sliding autonomy typically leads to a higher success rate compared to fully autonomous robots (as humans can help in case robots fail), as well as to faster task solving compared to fully manual operation (because it does not require the human to control every step in detail, which can be tedious and is especially difficult when controlling a multi-robot team). The downside may be, on the one hand, slower task solving compared to fully autonomous robots, and on the other hand, higher failure rates compared to the robot being under full control of a human.

Sliding autonomy can thus be considered a compromise/trade-off approach, aiming to find the ideal balance between human and machine activities depending on the respective situation, as it is the goal of SWS. One strategy may be to increase the autonomy level step by step, thus increasing the efficiency and reducing the human workload, but only until the performance of the robot starts to deteriorate [30]. Another aspect to be considered is that the ideal degree of autonomy may be dependent on the experience/skills of the human who is controlling and supporting the robot [28].

When trying to transfer sliding autonomy approaches from the robotics domain to human/AI work sharing scenarios, a basic difference must be considered: a human can rather easily see that a physical robot requires help or could become a safety hazard, but this may not be as easy or even impossible for a human working together with (and observing) an AI. To tackle this challenge, the AI4Work project aims to provide real-time SWS support by continuously (1) monitoring the current context of the work environment, (2) assessing if the AI was properly trained for this kind of situation and (3) suggesting (based on the assessment and additional context information) to which extent the AI may work autonomously and to which extent the human should be involved.

3 Sliding Work Sharing Vision

The vision of the AI4Work project is to improve communication and collaboration between humans, AI and robots. AI4Work intends to investigate practical methods and tools for optimal sharing of work between humans and AI/robots (the project will specifically focus upon AI solutions for diverse tasks including AI for intelligent

robotic systems). Due to the high level of uncertainty in modern organisations (in industry but also in healthcare, education, agriculture [34], [35]¹) an appropriate balance between human and machine activities (e.g., decision making [36] [37] must be found. The key assumption is that to cope with the required flexibility and dynamics, SWS, is likely to be the most appropriate for modern organisations. One of the key challenges in AI-supported working is an “appropriate interpretation of a context guiding machine or human to better understand the proposed support/recommendations/decisions” [38]. Due to the required high dynamics and flexibility in modern organisations, the context, under which work is carried out, changes rapidly. It is, therefore, important to identify online the current context and adapt AI/robots support based on it, and, at the same time, help operators understand the action taken or decision proposed by AI/robots. It is expected that this would lead to changes in attitudes towards AI- and robot-supported work in organisations [39].

4 Tools to Support Context Aware Sliding Work Sharing

4.1 Context Awareness

The Context Awareness component is a core element in rendering AI and robotic systems context-sensitive. It facilitates the extraction, interpretation, and representation of the operational circumstances under which collaborative work occurs, thereby enabling adaptive actions and recommendations aligned with the current environment. This component comprises three key modules:

- **Context Model:** Serves as a foundational knowledge base for representing collaborative human-AI/robot work across diverse scenarios. It defines a structured set of concepts and relationships that describe the stages, entities, attributes, and stakeholders involved in such collaboration.
- **Context Monitoring:** Continuously acquires raw data from sensors, systems, and various knowledge sources to detect changes in the environment. It identifies dynamic factors that influence the collaborative processes.
- **Context Extraction:** Processes the monitored data in alignment with the Context Model to derive the current context. This enables comparisons with historical contexts and supports informed decision-making, optimization, and system reconfiguration.

Within the AI4Work project, the Context Model is employed as a baseline to capture and formalize knowledge about human-AI/robot collaboration. The integration of Context Monitoring and Extraction services allows the system to identify and interpret context changes, ensuring adaptive and context-aware behaviour.

The proposed method establishes mechanisms for:

¹ According to [35] “When humans depend on automation to get their work done, they must be able to anticipate what happens, because they, not the machines, are responsible. ” and “Computer scientists should build devices to enhance and empower - not replace - humans.”

- Monitoring contextual parameters and detecting changes relevant to collaborative scenarios;
- Analysing quantitative relationships that affect context interpretation from multiple perspectives (e.g., user-centric, service-centric views);
- Defining entities and parameters critical for context monitoring;
- Investigating how monitoring mechanisms vary depending on the perspective adopted, as delineated by the Context Model.

By coordinating continuous monitoring and context extraction, the system transforms raw data into meaningful contextual knowledge. This capability is crucial for enabling adaptive decision-making and optimizing collaborative processes in dynamic human-AI/robot environments.

Key Challenges. The key challenges in Context Monitoring and Extraction components are:

- Can we retrieve all information from all needed sources?
AI4Work approach: the Context Monitoring solution defines a generic interface with an extendable and configurable standardised process. The question is can we really retrieve all information from the environment and AI4Work environment needed by the defined context model?
- Can we extract the context needed by the other AI4Work modules, based on the monitored information?
AI4Work approach: Using the context model, the monitored data is evaluated and the context extracted.

Context Model Concept. The AI4Work project employs an ontology-based approach for context modelling, leveraging ontologies' flexibility, expressiveness, and extensibility. Ontologies ensure a shared semantic understanding of context data across systems, enabling reasoning mechanisms to infer additional knowledge from implicitly stated information. Fig. 1 presents this approach.

Fig. 1. Context Awareness Approach

To identify the current contexts of services and processes, as well as the current context of the user in some situations, the proposed solution uses as information sources:

- data from the AI4Work components
- data from existing systems and sensors
- available knowledge from different systems

This information is used to extend base/core ontologies to meet the contexts of the systems in question and model the entities, and relationships between them.

Context Monitoring Concept. The objective of the **Context Monitoring** service is to transform raw sensor and system data into aggregated, structured monitoring data suitable for further processing. To achieve this, the service enables the monitoring of enterprise systems via various interfaces.

The core of the Context Monitoring service is a **modular monitoring process** that follows a standardized, extendable, and configurable architecture (Fig. 2). This process comprises three primary modules [19]:

- **Monitoring Module:** Responsible for acquiring data from systems and devices within enterprise environments via the Data Access Layer. Distributed monitoring services interact with this module to relay collected information. The monitoring services are designed to be extendable and configurable for diverse systems, without requiring tight coupling with other modules.
- **Parser Module:** Contains content parsers tailored to the diverse data formats and types captured by the monitoring services. The parsers enable access to heterogeneous data sources and may extract environmental properties relevant to context understanding. This module serves as the data interface for subsequent analysis.
- **Analyser / Monitoring Data Builder Module:** Correlates the parsed monitoring data, potentially incorporating environmental parameters, and constructs standardized monitoring datasets. These datasets are stored and provided to the Context Extraction service or other components requiring monitoring insights.

Fig. 2. Context Monitoring Process

Context Extraction Concept.

The Context Extraction service aims to derive and identify high-level contexts from the monitoring data produced by the Context Monitoring service, including both system-level and sensor-level raw data. The extracted contextual information is leveraged to improve productivity and operational efficiency in (semi-)automated environments, such as collaborative human-robot workspaces in domains like construction robotics, and to enhance knowledge representation.

The service is founded on a semantic representation model—the AI4Work Context Model—which integrates knowledge of collaborative human-AI/robot activities across various scenarios.

As illustrated in Fig. 3, the Context Extraction process involves the following key steps:

- **Context Identification:** Analyses the monitoring data received from the Context Monitoring service to extract contextual knowledge, such as identifying which robots, products, components, resources, or environmental conditions are involved, as well as tracking entities and activities referenced in the current operational context.
- **Context Reasoning:** Applies reasoning techniques to the identified contexts to derive higher-level or implicit contextual information that may not be directly observable through raw monitoring data. This step refines the context understanding by inferring relationships and dependencies.
- **Context Provisioning:** Compares the current identified contexts against historical contexts stored in the Context Repository to determine contextual similarities or trends. The results are made available to other services and modules within the AI4Work system.

Fig. 3. Context Extraction Process

The Context Extraction service builds upon technologies developed in the EU H2020 project SmartClide [25], while extending them significantly. Input data originates from diverse sources, including smart devices, control systems, and enterprise systems. Both structured and unstructured data are processed to determine the ongoing activities involving users, robots, products, equipment, or processes.

The outcome of the Context Extraction process—contextual information—is stored in a dedicated Context Repository. This repository annotates content with context

metadata, enabling advanced reasoning and adaptive decision-making in dynamic collaborative environments.

Innovations Targeted. New data to be modelled and monitored bring several innovations to the Context Awareness component, such as:

- **New Data Integration:** New data (e.g. localisation or human pose) to be modelled and monitored bring several innovations to the Context Awareness solution. It will expand the range of information that can be integrated and monitored.
- **Advanced Context Awareness:** Use new data types to enrich context information, optimising decision-making, task allocation, and reconfiguration in human-AI/robot collaboration.
- **Comprehensive Environmental Understanding:** Achieve a deep understanding of the environment, facilitating better monitoring and analysis of spatial relationships and interactions between humans and robots.

4.2 Sliding Work Sharing

The SWS Management component aims to facilitate dynamic sharing of work between humans and AI/robots. Depending on the respective work situation, the SWS Management shall decide about:

- the required degree of involvement of the human, considering the current level of uncertainty of the AI/robot,
- the (degree of) support to be provided to the human, depending on the human's experience and the current work situation.

The level of human/machine involvement is not considered to be fixed in advance but may vary at “runtime”, reacting to unplanned or unexpected events. This approach can be depicted as a “slider” between human and machine activity, which is adjusted dynamically, depending on the respective work situation. Three examples of the most typical situations are visualised as such a “slider” in the following figures:

- In case of high uncertainty of the AI in an unusual situation, the decision may fall to the human (see Fig. 4).
- In case of low uncertainty of the AI in a common situation, the decision/action may be suggested by the AI and confirmed by the human (see Fig. 5).
- In case of very low uncertainty of the AI in a very common situation, the decision may be automatically made by the AI, with human intervention possible but optional (see Fig. 6).

It should be pointed out, however, that the “slider” is not limited to the aforementioned situations but may move on the whole scale between “full human control” and “fully autonomous AI/robot”.

As some application scenarios may include several AI modules (e.g. one to support work planning in advance and one to support dynamic adaptations at plan execution time), the SWS Management may also support “dynamic sliding between two AI modules”. However, only the case of SWS between human and AI is considered in the following, aiming to keep this concept description simple.

Fig. 4. Possible SWS situation (i)¹

Fig. 5. Possible SWS situation (ii)

Fig. 6. Possible SWS situation (iii)

Key Challenges. The key challenges for the Sliding Work Sharing component in AI4Work are:

- Make the decision about the degree of human involvement vs. the autonomy of the AI/robot
AI4Work approach: the SWS Management will take several inputs from other components into account as basis for this decision, the most important being:
 - The uncertainty estimation regarding the AI/robot
 - The context information about the current work situation
 - The experience/skills of the human
- Make the decision about the need for re-planning/re-scheduling in case of an unexpected situation at “plan execution time”
AI4Work approach: the SWS Management will take several inputs from other components into account as basis for this decision, the most important being
 - The results of the plan’s validation
 - The context information about the current work situation

¹ This figure and the following include icons from Freepik

- The experience/skills and availability of human operator(s)
- The uncertainty estimation regarding the AI/robot
- How to adapt to the different pilot use cases, which consider a large variety of human-AI/robot work sharing situations?
AI4Work approach: the SWS Management will not be one monolithic component with a “one-size-fits-all” approach, but will rather provide generic reusable framework elements, which can be adapted and extended flexibly for each concrete pilot use case.

SWS Concept. SWS is defined as a work-sharing approach where the balance between human and machine (AI or robot) activities varies during the operation, depending on the situational context, machine-based confidence levels and human interactions [1] The SWS Management component aims to take these different inputs into account when deciding about the appropriate degree of human involvement – and/or the degree of support to the human – depending on the respective work situation.

A simplified conceptual workflow for SWS, indicating the role of the SWS Management component and its inputs from other AI4Work components, is depicted in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Sliding Work Sharing workflow¹

The main focus of the SWS Management is not on “planning work sharing in advance”, but to react to events/situations at “plan execution time”. Therefore, for the purpose of explaining the workflow of the SWS, we assume that there is a preliminary plan of tasks that is to be executed by the human or AI/robots in the case at hand. Our SWS workflow may be initiated by a human, a robot, some AI4Work technology (e.g. a Digital Twin that monitors the processes, the Context Awareness component detecting a situation change, or some AI service) or an external system. The “request for action” indicated on the left side of Fig. 7 should thus be considered a “generic placeholder” for “a work situation where some action/decision is required”. To enable the decision about the human/AI/robot involvement in the respective situation, several AI4Work technologies/components need to provide information:

¹ Figure includes icons from <https://www.freepik.com>

- The Context Awareness component extracts the contextual information about the current work situation
- The AI/robot suggests a decision/action based on the context information
- The Runtime Monitoring for Trustworthy AI takes the input of the AI components as well as the context information into account, this way estimating if the AI was properly trained for this kind of input data in the current situation
- The Human-centred Digital Twin needs to provide information about the skills/experience of the human

Based on these inputs, the SWS Management component then “decides” or “recommends” to what extent the AI/robot may work autonomously and if the actions/decision should be requested from (or checked/confirmed by) the human operator.

Depending on the specific application scenario, different basic degrees of automation may be possible. In some cases, the AI/robot may work autonomously as long as the uncertainty level of AI decisions is low. In other cases, the human operator may want to always stay in control, so that each decision/action suggested by the AI may have to be confirmed by the human.

In case of major disruptions that invalidate the original work plan (our preliminary plan of tasks), the SWS Management component may also decide that a re-calculation of the work plan is required. In such a case it will trigger other AI4Work components to do a re-planning.

The main element of the SWS Management component is the “sliding module”: this module is responsible for the “dynamic sliding decision at runtime”. Its “rule storage” contains pilot/use-case-specific rules that must be defined in advance. At runtime the “decision engine” applies these rules to the current input data (which is received from other AI4Work components and pilot-specific AI components) in order to dynamically decide about the recommended degree of AI autonomy and/or support to the human in the current situation.

Innovations Targeted. The SWS targeted innovations are:

- Application of the concepts of “sliding autonomy” [27-29] and “sliding decision making” [26] to the domain of “work sharing between human and AI”.
- Generic component/framework for SWS Management that can be adapted/extended to be applied in various pilot use cases.

5 Potential Applications

The current CA and SWS solutions are being tested in a scenario loosely based on a yard management pilot in the logistics domain from the AI4Work project.

The scenario is as follows:

- Imagine a queue of trucks that deliver material to a warehouse
- Usually the sequence is "first come, first served"
- Exception to the rule: a truck should be prioritized if it delivers material that is low on stock

The start point/trigger of the scenario assumes that there is low stock on a certain

product in the yard, a parameter that the context awareness component would extract from observing the whole yard management system. In this case the Context Awareness component will relate the materials stock, the rate at which these are needed, model these inputs (both to be read from the yard management system) and will be able to extract when the stock is low.

Fig. 8. Example of prioritization of a truck¹

Given the low stock trigger, an AI-based scheduler will consider the plan of loading/offloading of trucks in the yard and if there is a truck that brings the material needed, then it will suggest prioritizing this truck over the others (see Fig. 8). The SWS management will then decide to which extent a human must be involved in this prioritization. Input parameters for the SWS are for this example:

- Length of the queue (see rules example below, parameter `noOfTrucksInQueue`)
- The position of the truck in the queue (see rules example below, parameter `positionOfTruckToBePrioritized`)

The SWS internally applies fuzzy rules, e.g.:

- If the queue is short and the truck is near its front, it can be automatically prioritized
- If the queue is long and the truck is near its end, a human needs to be involved in the decision

The SWS will compute the sliding decision when it received sliding decision input data (coming from the other AI4Work components), fuzzifying the defined parameters and applying the fuzzy rules. The current development extends an out-of-the-box tool which we have extended and customised with custom parameters and rules for different application scenarios. This tool is *jFuzzyLogic* [40, 41] an open-source Java library. This library supports the standard Fuzzy Control Language (FCL), which is used to define input/output parameters, membership functions, and rule sets.

One of the parameters that is defined is the interval by which e.g. the number of trucks in the queue is considered low, medium or high. An example definition of these so-called membership functions would be:

¹ Figure includes icons from <https://www.freepik.com>

```

TERM LOW := (0, 1) (5, 1) (9, 0);
TERM MEDIUM := (5, 0) (9, 1) (11, 1) (15, 0);
TERM HIGH := (11, 0) (15, 1) (20, 1);

```

Rather than having static values, we have (partly overlapping) intervals and an input value may partly belong to two categories at the same time. Below is an example of the fuzzy rules above mentioned:

```

IF noOfTrucksInQueue IS LOW
THEN suggestedWorkSharingApproach IS AI_AUTONOMOUSLY;
IF noOfTrucksInQueue IS MEDIUM AND
positionOfTruckToBePrioritized IS
NEAR_THE_FRONT_OF_THE_QUEUE
THEN suggestedWorkSharingApproach IS HUMAN_ON_THE_LOOP;
IF noOfTrucksInQueue IS HIGH AND
positionOfTruckToBePrioritized IS
IN_THE_BACK_OF_THE_QUEUE
THEN suggestedWorkSharingApproach IS HUMAN_MANUALLY;

```

After receiving the “sliding decision input data” from the request, the SWS parametrizes and fuzzifies these inputs based on the membership functions specified. It then evaluates the rules using a fuzzy inference system and it calculates defuzzified output (crisp decision results). These results are then extracted and made available for use by other components.

6 Conclusions

This paper presented the concept and initial implementation of a context-aware Sliding Work Sharing (SWS) framework designed to support effective human-AI collaboration, illustrated by an application scenario from the logistics sector. By integrating dynamic context awareness with adaptive autonomy mechanisms, the AI4Work approach enables flexible redistribution of tasks between humans and AI/robot systems based on situational context, confidence levels, and user expertise. The framework’s modular design — featuring ontology-based context modelling, real-time monitoring and extraction, and fuzzy logic-based SWS decision making — demonstrates strong potential to improve operational efficiency, reduce cognitive load on human workers, and increase trust in AI-driven systems. The demonstrated yard management scenario highlights the feasibility and value of this approach in real-world logistics operations.

Future research directions will focus on several key areas:

- Scalability and Generalization: Extending the context-aware SWS framework to support more complex and larger-scale industrial scenarios, including multi-agent systems and cross-domain applications (e.g., healthcare, manufacturing, agriculture).
- Context Model Refinement: Enhancing the ontology to support more nuanced contextual features, such as emotional state, team dynamics, or organizational constraints, while also improving the cost-efficiency of data acquisition.

- Human-Centric Evaluation: Conducting longitudinal studies to better understand human acceptance, cognitive load, and trust dynamics in AI-assisted work environments under varying autonomy levels.
- Learning and Adaptation: Incorporating machine learning techniques to enable continuous learning from user behaviour and feedback, thereby improving the system's ability to predict optimal work sharing configurations.
- Ethical and Legal Considerations: Exploring regulatory, ethical, and transparency aspects related to dynamic work sharing between humans and AI, particularly in high-stakes decision-making contexts.

By addressing these directions, the AI4Work approach aims to contribute significantly to the development of trustworthy, flexible, and human-centred AI solutions for the workplace of the future.

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